

Detailed description of the Methodology used in the paper “Automated Data Extraction in Software Engineering SLRs: Promise, Pitfalls, and the Role of Human Oversight”

This document presents the methodological details used in the experiment described in the paper.

More specifically, the document includes: a brief introduction to the basic idea of the methodology, the dimensions considered, and the phases in which the experiment was organized.

Content

1. Introduction.....	2
2. Dimensions.....	2
3. Phases.....	4
4. Bibliography.....	7

1. Introduction

Given the breadth of the research questions to be addressed, we have designed a carefully structured experiment ensuring methodological rigor across all stages, which has enabled us to obtain solid initial findings on the capabilities and limitations of LLMs for SLR data extraction.

In summary, the experiment involves performing data extraction tasks within an SLR using both the traditional manual approach (human) and automated language processing tools (each of which receives the full-text PDFs as input). As mentioned in the paper, the data extraction phase in any SLR is notably lengthy and time-consuming. This is not only due to the typically large volume of primary studies to be analyzed—222, in our case— but also because of the cognitive effort required to interpret, infer, and consistently extract structured data from heterogeneous scientific texts. For this reason, and to ensure the volume of data generated by our experiment remained manageable and analyzable in depth, both the number of papers considered and the number of extraction questions posed had to be substantially reduced. To describe the experiment with maximum clarity and precision, we distinguish six core dimensions and four sequential phases in its design.

2. Dimensions

The first dimension concerns the *number of papers* included in the experiment. We considered a sample of around 5% of the 222 SLR articles—12 in total—to be sufficiently representative.

The second dimension is also related to the manageability of the volume of information handled in the experiment. In the data extraction phase of any SLR, a large *number of questions* is usually asked. In particular, our SLR defined 20 questions: 9 about Quality Assurance (QA) and 11 questions specific to Data Extraction (DE). For the experiment, we considered using around a third (6) of the total SLR questions sufficient to cover a variety of questions and answer types. The selected questions are included in Table 1. Set of questions used in the experiment

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.

All the questions defined for data extraction in our SLR are deductive; that is, the information to be extracted is not normally found *as-is* in the text of the analyzed works but requires inference.

Table 1. Set of questions used in the experiment

ID	Question	Answer Type
QA01	Does the study directly address data management or data governance?	Boolean
QA04	Is a novel technological approach proposed? If so, is it implemented or tested in a real-world environment?	Boolean
QA07	Does the study discuss the potential generalization of results and conclusions to other contexts or case studies?	Boolean
DE02	What specific subdomains of smart cities are addressed in the study?	List of categories
DE03	Which aspects of data management, as proposed by DAMA, are explicitly or implicitly addressed in the study?	List of categories
DE08	Which digital twin maturity level, according to (Klar et al., 2024), if any, is considered in the study?	Category

The *number of human experts* involved in conducting the experiment constitutes the third dimension. Although it could have been carried out by a single expert, we have tried to avoid that a single opinion can spoil the experiment (in fact, the SLR methodology (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007) encourages each paper to be evaluated by more than one expert). For this reason, the experiment was carried out by three human experts (the authors). Their diverse academic backgrounds, ages, and genders are noted descriptively: the research questions do not reflect the need for the analysis of these factors.

The fourth dimension is the *number of automated tools* to consider, and of course, which ones. For the same reason mentioned above, and to mitigate tool-specific bias, we included three LLM-based tools. The selection of tools was also carried out in a detailed and justified manner, through a comparison of a wide range of available tools (a summary of this study is also included in another file of this Supplementary Material). The alternative analysis process concluded with the selection of ChatGPT, ChatPDF, and Google NotebookLM, all in their free-of-charge versions. This decision was based on criteria such as reproducibility, availability (accessible through web browsers), ease of use, and diversity of purpose, thereby ensuring the inclusion of tools accessible to professionals who may not necessarily be experts. The relevance of the tools was also considered based on their presence in previous studies, as well as their novelty, particularly in the case of NotebookLM.

The fifth dimension is directly related to the second research question of our study. In the experiment, different *orders of data extraction* were distinguished, depending on whether the extraction is first performed manually by the human expert, and then repeated using automated tools (we will refer to this order as *pre*), or vice versa (*idem* order *post*). To ensure an unbiased comparison, each paper was independently reviewed by two human experts under different extraction orders. These two evaluations are technically distinct, as the *post* condition explicitly captures potential influence from prior exposure to AI-generated results. Therefore, no consensus was sought between human reviewers: enforcing agreement would have undermined the experimental goal of assessing whether such exposure can bias human judgment. Instead, both sets of human extractions were retained

independently, allowing the study to capture genuine variability between extractions performed under different cognitive conditions.

The last dimension refers to the different variants in the *grouping of extraction* (directly linked to the third research question). Three different types of extraction have been considered (partially conditioned by the characteristics of the chosen tools).

Sequential extraction (code S) means that all questions on a given paper are asked continuously (sequentially), and that the same procedure is followed for each one of the evaluated papers. This type of extraction was performed by human experts (it is their natural attitude towards this type of task) and was mimicked in the ChatGPT tool by considering all papers in a single conversation/session (taking one paper after another).

The *isolated type of extraction* (code I) differs in that each paper is handled in a separate conversation/session. This type of extraction was applied to all automated tools.

The third type, *block extraction* (code B), involves loading all papers simultaneously, after which the questions are posed. This approach is incompatible with ChatGPT's conversational design. Preliminary attempts to use this type of grouping with ChatPDF were discouraging, as the tool (at least in its free version) yielded unsatisfactory results and inconsistent outputs. Thus, block extraction was applied only in NotebookLM.

3. Phases

A *preliminary/preparatory Phase 0* was necessary to set up technical infrastructure that would support the subsequent phases of the experiment. Three spreadsheets (one for each human expert) were created to record both manual extractions and tool-generated answers.

In addition, a relational database was designed and created to have a unified searchable instrument: this database was fed with all the information collected in the three spreadsheets mentioned above (for reproducibility, all this information is provided in a CSV file in this Supplementary Material). In addition, the prompts provided to the three tools were carefully designed and refined, based on multiple preliminary trials conducted on other samples of papers, aiming to develop highly reliable prompts that would achieve greater precision (also in this Supplementary Material).

In *Phase 1*, we defined the *sample of papers* and the *set of questions*. On the one hand, as detailed in the *number of papers dimension*, this number was set to 12 (5% of the total number of papers in the extraction phase of our SLR). The selection of the

papers was made by a strictly random process among the 222 available papers (the list of selected papers can be found in this Supplementary Material). The 12 papers were distributed into 3 groups of 4 papers each, assigning two groups (i.e. 8 papers in total) to each human expert. The groups were distributed in such a way that each expert shared one group with each of the other two experts (see Figure 1. Distribution of the sample of papers). This distribution ensures that each paper is evaluated by two different human experts, one performing the extraction before tool usage (*pre-extraction order*) and the other after (*post-extraction order*).

Figure 1. Distribution of the sample of papers

On the other hand, regarding the *number of questions dimension*, the questions were selected based on objective criteria: choosing questions from both QA and DE and ensuring diversity of answer types. QA-type questions always had boolean answers, while DE-type questions admitted more varied responses. We chose only those DE questions whose answers corresponded to a closed list of categories (or a single category in one case), since these are easier to handle consistently. More open-ended questions (e.g., open lists or even free-text responses) were excluded from the experiment as they would introduce variability difficult to manage in practice.

The final set of questions ultimately used in the experiment —three QA-type questions and three DE-type questions— appears in Table 1. Set of questions used in the experiment (for reproducibility and consistency, question IDs match those from the original SLR set, and are therefore not numbered consecutively). For context, our SLR focused on data management and governance in the development and use of digital twins for smart cities. Although all selected questions require some inference, DE03 and DE08 are particularly demanding, as they require knowledge external to the primary studies being analyzed. Question DE03 refers to the well-known (to human experts) DAMA framework on data management (International Data Management Association, 2017) but without explicitly referencing it. This means that the tools must rely on their internal knowledge of DAMA, acquired during training, to detect implicit references to it. Question DE08, in turn, refers to one specific work (Klar, Arvidsson and Angelakis, 2024) that the tools must locate

and use as a reference. The added difficulty in this case is that this work was published after the analyzed studies, making it impossible for those papers to explicitly reference it. Therefore, responding accurately to this question requires higher reasoning.

Phase 2 is undoubtedly the most complex of all, as it is where the actual *data extraction* takes place. Each expert conducted seven test configurations, explained below using Expert X as an example (see Figure 1. Distribution of the sample of papers). The other two experts followed equivalent procedures.

Test 1. *Manual-S*. Expert X performs the extraction in the conventional way, reading each article and answering the questions according to his or her understanding of the text. This task is repeated (sequentially, code S) for each paper in Group 1.

Test 2. *ChatGPT-I*. Expert X initiates a ChatGPT session, enters the initial prompts designed in Phase 0 to guide the tool's behavior, uploads the PDF file of the first paper from Group 2, and then continues with the specific prompts corresponding to each of the predefined questions for that paper. This process is repeated for the four papers in Group 2, starting a new ChatGPT session for each paper (which means that the extraction grouping is isolated, code I).

Test 3. *ChatPDF-I*. Expert X performs a completely identical test to the previous one, but this time using the ChatPDF tool.

Test 4. *NotebookLM-I*. Expert X performs the same test as the previous two, but this time using the NotebookLM tool.

Test 5. *ChatGPT-S*. Expert X starts a single session in ChatGPT, and sequentially (code S), loads each paper from Group 2, asking all the questions for each of the papers.

Test 6. *NotebookLM-B*. Expert X logs into NotebookLM, loads all papers of Group 2 in block (code B), and asks the questions for each specific paper.

Test 7. *Manual-S*. Expert X repeats Test 1, but this time for Group 2 of papers, for which (s)he has prior knowledge of the answers previously obtained from the tools.

To complete the experimental setup, Expert Y performed Test 1 on Group 3 of papers (and the remaining tests on Group 1), and Expert Z performed Test 1 on Group 2 of papers (and the rest of tests on Group 3). This ensures that each paper has been evaluated by two human experts: once before performing the extraction using tools (*pre-extraction order*), and once after (*post-extraction order*). Moreover, we ensure that all experts evaluated the same number of papers under both conditions (both in the *pre-* and *post-extraction orders*), maintaining balance for comparative analyses performed in the next Phase, and minimizing expert-related bias.

Additionally, all papers have been evaluated by all three tools, and all *groupings of extraction (S, I, B)* have been applied as appropriate.

Finally, *Phase 3* involved *analyzing the data collected* in the database described in Phase 0, through custom-designed database views and advanced processing using Jupyter notebooks. The results and discussion of this analysis are presented in the corresponding sections of the paper.

4. Bibliography

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